

METHODOLOGY OF CONDUCTING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of a study of the needs in learning English of first-year students in non-linguistic areas of undergraduate study. The necessity of conducting such research at a university is substantiated, since it helps to identify the main goals, motives, and methods of effective mastery of a foreign language.

INTRODUCTION

A foreign language plays a significant role in the life of a representative of modern society, since its study is directly related to the development of a person's cultural level and improvement of him as an individual. In addition, knowledge of a foreign language is one of the key components of the successful professional activity of a modern, competitive specialist for effectively solving professional problems in dynamically changing realities. Modern reality is such that students of non-linguistic areas demonstrate an ambiguous attitude towards the subject "Foreign language". For a significant proportion of students, a motivational and emotional deficit in relation to a foreign language begins to form in school and is subsequently transferred to the process of studying it at a university, since this discipline is often not directly related to the life plans of students. Often students have a negative attitude towards this subject as very difficult, almost impossible to master [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The needs analysis method can serve as the basis for developing a work program for the "Foreign Language" discipline, practical classes, as well as extracurricular activities. This method includes determining goals, level of proficiency, degree of motivation, expectations of students from studying a foreign language at a university and assessing previous experience in mastering it.

The needs analysis method is based on the achievements and capabilities of students, rather than emphasizing their shortcomings, allowing students to determine the knowledge and skills that they acquired in the process of learning a foreign language. It is characterized

by continuity, as it is carried out throughout the entire program of the “Foreign Language” discipline.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The planning process includes the following steps [2].

- Goal setting, i.e. What information do you need to create a workable course syllabus?
- Determination and selection of various techniques and methods: will you use a questionnaire, an observation method, conduct a conversation, a group survey, assign an assignment to write an essay or draw a diagram, drawing, timeline. When choosing a method for obtaining information, it is necessary to take into account the age of the students, the direction of training (language or non-linguistic department). To obtain the most complete picture, it is recommended to use a complex of various methods.
- Selecting the form of application, time of implementation, method of analyzing the data obtained.
- Determine the language (native or foreign) you will use. This step depends on the level of language proficiency of a particular group.
- Program development.

The reasons for decreased motivation can be divided into two groups: reasons depending on the teacher and reasons depending on the student. Among the reasons depending on the teacher are: incorrect selection of educational material and teaching methods, low level of proficiency in modern teaching methods, inability to build relationships with students and organize their interaction with each other, and the personal characteristics of the teacher. The reasons for the decrease in motivation depending on students are: low level of knowledge, lack of understanding of one's own motives for educational activities and methods of independent acquisition of knowledge, and undeveloped relationships in the study group.

A low level of extrinsic motivation indicates the existence of students' motivational potential, which needs to be updated by teaching staff in the process of learning a foreign language. The more students perceive the teacher as a controller and leader, the less intrinsically motivated they become. Conversely, the perception of one's autonomy and freedom on the part of the teacher increases students' internal motivation.

A comfortable atmosphere in the classroom, entertaining tasks, self-analysis and self-esteem are effective ways to develop student motivation. In addition, the student's freedom to choose the content of tasks, methods, learning style and a holistic learning strategy lead to increased internal motivation in learning a foreign language.

Teachers often use the term self-motivated student to describe those who are internally motivated and do not need external reinforcement. Intrinsically motivated students can achieve good results if their learning activities are aimed at productive goals. In a certain sense, it is promising that intrinsic motivation is not an innate characteristic; rather, it is acquired through the process of gaining experience. Teachers need to know that by teaching students to use incentive behavior strategies, they help develop personal internal motivation in them. Such motivation is useful not only in the educational process, but also in performing various tasks outside of class. It must be remembered that too high a level of motivation

causes excessive tension and leads to a decrease in efficiency and negative emotional reactions [2].

It should be noted that the majority of students (73%) found it difficult to choose their own goals for learning a foreign language, proposed in the third section of the questionnaire. This result showed that students do not have a sufficient level of autonomy and consciousness in the learning process and prefer a passive learning style. To solve this problem, the teacher, together with the student, identified personal goals for learning a foreign language, ways to achieve them, and recorded them in an individual learning plan.

The methodological experiment we conducted showed that the needs analysis method had a positive effect on both participants in the educational process. Thus, students began to better understand themselves, their strengths and weaknesses, as well as why they are studying a foreign language, learned to set realistic goals, determined what language skills and abilities they possess and which ones need to be developed, responsibility, independence and activity increased. The most important achievement was that students became more motivated, seeing the teacher's interest and support [3].

CONCLUSION

Thus, in our opinion, there is a need to carry out a procedure for analyzing the needs for studying a foreign language at a university, which allows the teacher to competently develop a work program for the "Foreign Language" discipline and a plan for extracurricular activities, including language competitions, scientific and practical conferences, and Olympiads of various levels. In addition, understanding the needs of each student, be more flexible in choosing forms, methods and techniques of training, and provide the necessary assistance in overcoming difficulties.

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